

AIS Data Challenges and Opportunities 2024

A report from a workshop to build capacity for aquatic invasive species (AIS)
data best practices in the Upper Mississippi River Basin

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Workshop Overview

In October 2024, the Midwest Big Data Innovation Hub hosted a two-day, professionally facilitated online workshop focused on developing two outputs: (1) a community guidance document on critical challenges for cross-sector aquatic invasive species (AIS) data management and sharing (this report), and (2) a research development roadmap to kickstart proposal planning and teaming for the AIS data community.

Participants came from a variety of academic institutions and government agencies, and included research faculty, academic staff, Extension staff, and practitioners, including AIS managers. The workshop included facilitated, small focus-group style discussions with participants.

Funding for this workshop came from National Science Foundation awards 2136085 and 1916613.

Community Input

Workshop participants and other AIS experts provided pre-meeting input on topics related to AIS data management via an online survey form. The meeting organizers and facilitators synthesized and summarized their input prior to the workshop, used that information to help guide the meeting agenda, and then integrated the additional information provided by participants during the meeting. This document represents the authors' interpretation of the community input and meeting participants' thoughts during the workshop. It is not intended to be the authoritative view of AIS data management and any errors or omissions are the responsibility of the authors, not the workshop participants. We thank the participants for their insightful contributions.

Executive Summary

This report documents best practices that workshop participants shared for supporting effective, efficient, and collaborative work within the current system of aquatic invasive species (AIS) management. In addition, the discussion surfaced many tensions that point toward opportunities for more systemic changes in order to better support the system overall.

The core cycle of work in this field is a process of collecting, analyzing, and making decisions about AIS, using data. This cycle is supported by the people who work with AIS data: their capacity, their collaborations, and their sharing, which are further supported by a foundation of data management that allows the field as a whole to organize, access, and utilize data in the long-term.

Section summaries

Decision-making to prevent the spread and to mitigate the impacts of AIS is the core purpose of collecting AIS data. While decision-making is primarily led by AIS managers and other policy stakeholders (with the public playing important roles in supporting funding and following through on intervention recommendations), researchers also have an important role to play in ensuring the right data is available and usable for decision making. (see page 6)

Data collection involves a wide range of people with different sets of knowledge and motivations. Often moments of data collection coincide with interactions with other important goals such as public buy-in and education. The design of methods and tools need to balance the needs of the different users, the context of use, and the need for data quality. (see page 10)

Analysis is a critical step to bridge from raw data to decision making, and it's especially important in fields like AIS where the data sets are large, the topics are complex, and the decision makers (often the public) have varied baseline knowledge to build from. Analysis is often the aspect of working with AIS data that gets the most focus, but it relies heavily on the others to function effectively and efficiently. (see page 12)

Collaboration and communication are both core to AIS work as researchers, managers, the public, and others connect and share about AIS prevention and management. Doing this work in collaborative ways supports involving people more meaningfully in the process, and addressing issues of capacity that arise from not having enough people for collection, intervention, and other tasks. (see page 13)

Capacity—having the people, incentives, and skills to work with AIS data—influences every part of this work, from collection of data to documenting and sharing best practices. Limitations in capacity lead to a wide variety of challenges and spur individual workarounds, which themselves can reduce capacity in the system overall. There are many best practices to learn from, ranging from individual to systemic actions. (see page 16)

Data sharing is particularly important for people focused on AIS because it's so easy for invasive species themselves to cross human jurisdictional boundaries. Effective management, as well as research, requires sharing information and knowledge across projects, geographies, institutions, and time. Making this sharing not just possible, but also useful requires collaboration and intentional data management, which both take time and incentives to do well. (see page 20)

Data management practices set the foundation for all other aspects of AIS data work, but often they're an afterthought. The organization, long-term storage, and accessibility of data allows their users to analyze and make decisions, and also supports their sharing and collaboration. Maintaining strong practices feels like it requires extra time and effort upfront, with potential benefits unclear, and there often aren't strong current standards to lean on. (see page 21)

The Core Cycle of AIS Data Work

The core cycle of work in this field is a process of collecting, analyzing, and making decisions about aquatic invasive species (AIS), using data along the way.

Decision-Making

Decision-making to prevent the spread and to mitigate the impacts of AIS is the core purpose of collecting AIS data. While decision-making is primarily led by AIS managers and other policy stakeholders (with the public playing important roles in supporting funding and following through on intervention recommendations), researchers also have an important role to play in ensuring the right data is available and usable for decision making.

◇Core tensions about decision-making

Removal is extremely difficult, so prioritizing a focus on prevention is critical. But it's challenging to measure what is effective in prevention, making it hard to know what to do.

Measuring prevention is a counterfactual, since you can't see what doesn't happen. Yet at the same time, prevention is a top priority for AIS managers and researchers. To make decisions that lead to successful prevention, there's a need for both modeling that shows what the outcomes could be with and without intervention, as well as information about what does *and* doesn't work when it comes to prevention. Not only is it difficult to prove what didn't happen, there's little incentive to publish negative results, such as when prevention programs are not effective.

“There's no journal for negative results when things don't work (like when prevention programs are not effective) so there's no incentive to share the evaluation data or outcomes.”

“Prevention is super in counterfactual land — how do we prove something didn't happen because we did it?”

Long-term data sets, showing change over extended periods of time, can be important to public perception and decision-making, but they are challenging to maintain.

Trends in AIS populations over an extended period of time help with decision-making because it's possible to see what kind of impact species are actually having when they are present in an environment. If the impact is less than anticipated (for whatever reason) intervention resources could be targeted elsewhere. But, managers need to have the data to know what the impact is, and be able to communicate clearly to the public and other stakeholders. For more information about long-term data management, see the Data Management section (page 21).

“[What we’re seeing with the milfoil data] is that in lakes where we didn’t do anything, it’s present, but not more than the native plants. We were doing outreach saying, ‘these things are bad!’ but they’ve acclimated over time, and this has scaled [down] the urgency of responding — particularly because sometimes the management tactics are more harmful than the species.”

Different contexts and data users will have different considerations when making decisions from data — there’s complexity in using the data in practice.

Use of data for making decisions about AIS can vary across different contexts. Things like assessing what level of risk is acceptable, or what information is needed to make decisions, need to be assessed by the community of practice that knows that specific context. In addition, it’s often useful for the decision-makers to have the data available in a visualization for interpretation.

“The researchers didn’t want to say, ‘here’s the cut-off line for a high- or low-risk species’ — the decision had to be made by the community of practice that understands what an acceptable level of risk is. We had to have a lot of conversations with researchers and agencies about what is the acceptable level of risk. ‘None’ is the best, but it’s not feasible — and every state has its own opinions for policy.”

Decision makers are under pressure to make the right decision, and without access to data to inform their response and show the potential consequences, they can end up not taking action rather than making a choice they’re not confident in.

There’s a lot of pressure on decision makers to quickly make decisions about what interventions and actions to take on AIS, as the potential for spread or infestation can be so damaging. However, there’s sometimes a perception that there isn’t the data available to inform what the response should be or what will happen as a result. When those data do exist, it’s in journals or databases, inaccessible to the management reality. The data not only needs to be available, but also at the right time, with data that is up-to-date or even in real-time, and easily accessible.

“There’s a big gap between the data that exists and the high pressure decisions that have to be made; the chasm is a reality. It’s something we’re hoping to try to fill in.”

Communication and decision-making are closely connected, and the public and other stakeholders who may be less familiar with AIS data are a key part of the audience.

To make informed decisions, AIS managers and stakeholders need to have data in a form that communicates the options and what they’ve learned. Once the decision is made, it then needs to translate the implications to the public or other stakeholders. Researchers have a role to play in sharing analysis of what’s been learned about AIS, but they ultimately are not (usually) the decision-makers.

“We work with social scientists and take recommendations from them, but we also have to make sure that makes sense to us. We did a study in 2012 where they made recommendations on how to proceed on framing messages for the largest impact for a Great Lakes-wide, restoration intensive project. We had to make decisions about what we’d recommend for gardeners to

include in their water gardens, etc. We have risk assessment data that was collected by another group – we are making decisions based on [those data] and working with regulations across the Great Lakes as well. We take it all and digest it, for making those recommendations [in a way that aligns with all the policies].”

“How we’re framing things [at a state agency] — we’re giving recommendations that are feasible and actionable, that people are likely and able to do — is based off of data. We have to create the materials that we can disseminate and provide to the public.”

“Every rule our agency might develop needs data behind it [so that] it is solid and presentable to the public.”

◇Core best practices for decision-making

Model and forecast the likely places where AIS will be introduced or spread to, based on what’s happening on the ground.

Being able to model and see potential areas of concern for AIS can support managers and decision-makers to prioritize where they invest resources to try to slow down spread. To effectively develop these types of models, researchers must work with local managers to ensure the model is pulling the needed data, assessing the conditions on the ground, and other factors that make it a workable decision-making tool. Modeling requires substantial capacity and skill to execute.

Have real-time data available to decision-makers, particularly for new AIS in order to understand where it’s going and to quickly share the information.

Often, data is deposited on a schedule that is slower than the spread of AIS — such as tranches of data added on an annual basis. Particularly for new species, having this data closer to real-time supports decision makers to respond to the changing conditions quickly. This should be built into data management plans when possible.

Invest in the public communication of the results and challenges with AIS.

The public are an important stakeholder in decision-making, supporting funding and ultimately being the ones who take action on many of the interventions that are needed for long-term prevention. Being able to share results and challenges in a way that is clear and understandable to the public is critical to support their buy-in and participation.

Use clear and thoughtful processes for incorporating data into decision-making, such as Structured Decision-Making to make collaborative decisions using data.

Processes like Structured Decision-Making use facilitated conversation to support people to effectively assess potential decisions in the context of potential trade-offs and decisions they must make. These kinds of processes can involve different stakeholders working together closely. See additional discussion in the Collaboration and Communication section, page 13.

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Other best practices include:

- Use [placer.ai](#) to help show specific hot spots.
- Use data to show the public the severity and concerns about AIS by showing what the current status is.

Data Collection

Within AIS work, collection of data is completed by a range of different people, including managers, inspectors, and citizen science volunteers. These diverse types of data collectors can mean that consistency and verification of data can widely vary. In addition, some of the major points of data collection — such as watercraft inspections — are also an important moment of public buy-in and education, meaning that the interaction must support multiple outcomes.

Data collection is supported by designing collection tools that suit the setting and people involved in the process, as well as having a clear system for verification and quality control.

◇Core tensions about data collection

People doing data collection may not know why specific nuance and data details are valuable to researchers, and so may not prioritize collecting them.

As mentioned in tensions about capacity, over time people transition to the practices that feel most effective and efficient for them, rather than sticking to a protocol that collects the details that are valuable to other AIS stakeholders. Understanding why those details are being collected can help ensure that there's fidelity in collection.

Structured data collection methods can create artificial barriers to a more organic conversation, which in some settings would yield more accurate information or meet other goals.

Since a goal of AIS programs is education, data collection methods can help build buy-in as inspectors interact with the public and help support awareness about prevention and mitigation measures for AIS. But this requires tools that can support the conversation between the data collector and the water-users. When the tools are highly structured, such as having to go through a tablet-based, drop-down question list during a watercraft inspection, it may be more challenging to support this relationship building.

While collecting more nuanced and in-depth information is useful for researchers, it's time consuming and messy to input it in a consistent way. Context can get lost for the sake of efficiency or accessibility.

This becomes a trade-off between having nuanced data (both qualitative and quantitative) and being able to input quantitative data into a model that leads to a trustworthy result. Context can get lost when trying to input the quantitative data into a model. But when data collection is nuanced and detailed, there's not always a good home for it nor capacity for analyzing and using that additional information (such as detail from inspection conversations).

“[In the data set] there has to be consistency about what 3 means — that it means the same thing from one person to another person. I have to shove the data into a box I can trust, but a manager may find that too reductive — we've lost the context of the 3 by doing that, and that's a tradeoff.” - AIS researcher

◇ **Core best practices for collection of data**

Design collection tools to support buy-in with the public through conversation and education.

Some managers are using paper surveys in order to facilitate the collection of additional information that comes through conversation with the public during inspections, and to allow for less linear conversations. However, these tools may be harder to input in the long-term. Designing the standardized collection tools to support conversations, education, and collection of relevant nuance can help support buy-in.

“You get more information on paper than with the tablet — the tablet forces you to go one question at a time, and the conversation is more mechanical.” - AIS Manager

Have a protocol for verification and a system for quality control built into the data collection tool (such as requiring a photo with citizen science reports).

A clear protocol for quality assurance and quality control of data collection (particularly from volunteers) helps ensure that the data meets the quality expectations before it is added to the data set. Examples can include requiring photos or other relevant reference points with the submission. Having validation built into collection tools also helps with data quality, preventing people from adding content that doesn't fit.

“It can be effective to build a tool that has validation built-in, because then people can't add inoperable data in the first place.” - AIS Researcher

Analysis

Analysis is a critical step to bridge from raw data to decision making, and it's especially important in a field where the data sets are large, the topics are complex, and the decision makers (often the public) have varied baseline knowledge to build from. Analysis is often the aspect of working with AIS data that gets the most focus, but it relies heavily on the others to function effectively and efficiently. Many tensions about analysis connect closely to data sharing and capacity.

◇Core tension about analysis

Since qualitative and quantitative data have such different structures and analysis processes, it's difficult to collect them and use them within the same stream.

The protocols for collection, management, and analysis are different, and there's a need for different skills and capacity to use these two different sets of data. Qualitative data skills tend to be rare in the AIS space. There's an opportunity to analyze qualitative data for opportunities to support behavior change, but capacity is limited to support this exploration.

“[Inspectors] have an option to enter whatever in text or narrative, and I spent so many hours reviewing the text. [Recently we] decided we won't look at this anymore...even though there's good information, it's great to have the background, but we don't have time for so much data.”

Other tensions include:

- Sometimes, it's not clear what people are collecting data for from the beginning of their effort. Once data is collected, there's a desire to use it in a lot of different ways.
- Understanding the chain of interactions between AIS and the environment can enable collaborations between different disciplines, which requires shared data.

◇Core best practices for analysis

Best practices raised by the participants about analysis primarily had to do with ways to increase capacity — such as using tools to support data analysis, using shared tools that process data, and developing systems to share or access people with specialized skills. See additional discussion in the Capacity section, page 16.

Human Dimensions

Before AIS data is collected, analyzed, or put to use, people—through their work, skills, and relationships—set the stage for work with AIS data. This includes through **collaboration and communication**, as well as **data sharing**, which support bringing together researchers, managers, collaborators, and the public around AIS prevention and management, as well as **capacity**, where there are the people, incentives, and skills to work with AIS data.

Collaboration and Communication

Collaboration and communication practices are core to AIS work as researchers, managers, collaborators, policymakers, and the public connect and share about AIS prevention and management. Collaboration between different groups of users supports both involving people more meaningfully in the process, and addressing issues of capacity that arise from not having enough people for collection, intervention, and other tasks.

Collaboration and communication is enhanced and improved through relationships, new tools, and additional capacity to share and communicate.

◇Core tensions about collaboration and communication

When managers and researchers collaborate, there is a balance between addressing priorities of each group within the limited capacity available.

Managers and researchers have many overlapping goals, but they may prioritize those goals differently. For example, sometimes managers want to build relationships with watercraft users to change behavior as a higher priority than completing precise data collection. There's a need to recognize and balance these priorities in all AIS work, because so much of it is inherently collaborative.

“There's a natural tension between management decisions and research interest. The watercraft inspection is a great program, but [a lot of stuff happens that is justified for management reasons], but if I were to design a study to do things, it's not what I would do. [For all of us] to leverage the capacity of our management partners as part of their day to day work, it requires a lot of effort to bridge that gap.”

Communicating and coordinating is critical to not duplicating efforts, but it takes time and capacity.

Given capacity limitations for everyone in the AIS world, the careful balance described above requires communication and expectation setting about data collection, management, and sharing to avoid duplication. For example, without knowing where other agencies are doing sampling, the same areas could be sampled often. A good option for addressing this coordination is to build relationships with others, but with turnover and limited capacity this can be challenging.

“Coordinating is really left up to our capacity — it’s individual staff members reaching out, but then when there’s turnover...it would be more effective to maintain relationships long-term.”

Communicating outcomes and needs to the public is critical to support funding.

Public buy-in (and even participation in collection) is critical to success in AIS work. Funding is supported because the public cares about their local bodies of water. Communication of what’s learned from data collection is part of an important cycle of informing the public of best practices, lessons learned, and new needs, supporting more participation and funding support.

Other tensions include:

- Researchers from different disciplines need to know the context of where data came from in order to use it for good decisions.
- It's hard to know what data would be relevant to others (and what of others' data would be relevant to you) – it requires extra steps and more information that may not feel available.

◇**Core best practices for collaboration and communication**

Build tools with people who understand what is needed for managers and decision-makers.

Having a collaborator involved who understands what different actors within the AIS landscape need as part of the process of building data tools can help ensure that the tools serve the specific needs of different groups of people. This is closely connected to Decision-Making (see page 6).

Share back what’s learned at many levels to increase buy-in.

In many places, support from the public is critical to supporting long-term funding and attention, and there’s a need to share back what’s learned in data collection processes to show progress or areas of concern. This messaging and communication happens at various levels of detail through websites, as well as local presentations and sharing.

Use shared tools that can work in many settings.

Digital tools can support many different people participating in data collection and data management to coordinate and share across different locations. Tools like ArcGIS Field Maps allow users to see where others have uploaded samples, for greater awareness of where collection or sampling is happening. In addition, uploading data to shared tools, including places like the USGS or organizational repositories, can also facilitate awareness of shared and available data, and make it easier to access. This closely connects to Data Collection (page 10).

Develop communication tools with future decision-making in mind.

AIS data is ultimately used to make decisions about where to prioritize interventions or resources to support mitigation and prevention of AIS. Communication tools should be designed to support informed decision-making, helping to visualize and model data in ways that managers, researchers, policy-makers, and the public can understand and respond to.

Support adoption of best practices across the system.

Efforts such as these workshops and other opportunities to learn and share best practices help support adoption of best practices in a variety of research and management contexts, improving the overall system. In particular, opportunities for AIS stakeholders (including managers, researchers, and the public) to learn from each other and understand the constraints and opportunities of each role is a critical part of strengthening the use of consistent best practices.

Support long-term coordination between entities that may be involved in work that could duplicate or reinforce.

Building long-lasting relationships that lead to coordination between organizations and entities working in similar areas, with similar populations, and/or toward similar goals can support reducing duplication and strengthening on-going efforts.

Use processes like Structured Decision-Making to clarify the steps of using data to make decisions.

For more information, see the section on Decision-Making (page 6).

Capacity

Capacity—having the people, incentives, and skills to work with AIS data—is foundational to enabling AIS researchers, managers, and other collaborators to be successful in their goals. Capacity influences every part of working with AIS data, from collection of data to documenting and sharing best practices. Limitations in capacity lead to a wide variety of challenges in working with AIS data, ranging from not being able to use all the data collected to inconsistency in the data as people fall into their own habits without sufficient training and guidance.

Capacity can be enhanced and improved in a variety of ways, including adding staff and time available, increasing standardization and training for data literacy, and using supplementary and supportive tools.

◇Core tensions about capacity

Staff capacity for data is the most effective way to address capacity concerns, but there are a limited number of qualified researchers.

It takes years for a researcher to learn data skills and appreciation. Interest in data is a prerequisite to building the deep skills needed to manage and support data. While there may be some one-off or short-term ways to build appreciation for data, or take steps toward data literacy, ultimately the type of data scientist needed to support AIS research requires years of training and is a highly-sought skill set across many industries.

Building data literacy is critical to effectively utilize the systems of data, and this takes time.

Many people within the data ecosystem can build and strengthen their data literacy to more effectively collect, manage, and use data, but this process takes time — often years to build a deep set of skills. The time is needed for a range of things, from appreciating and being excited about data, to learning the best practices and tips that make data use effective. When the system makes it easier for people to adopt best practices, the timeline can be shortened.

“Building this capacity takes time — takes a long time. It’s not a workshop or a paper reading here or a hand out at this moment. Whole courses, years of assisted mentorship, depending on what [we’re] talking about.”

When there’s not sufficient capacity to train and retrain people in consistent methods of data collection and management, people will eventually start doing their own thing.

Even if people working with data begin with the grounding and training about things like expectations for data management, processing, and review of data, without reinforced training and belief in the underlying reasoning they will adapt their methods to what makes most sense (and is most effective) for them in that moment, sometimes resulting in data that strays from the intention. Sufficient capacity is needed to train (and retrain) to keep everyone who is collecting and managing the data aligned.

“We’re constantly having to retrain people in data collection and management, and then people start doing slightly different things.”

While collected data may have a lot of nuance and detail, there’s rarely the capacity to review and use it.

While additional data (especially qualitative or open-ended) adds depth, it takes substantial capacity and time to review and analyze it, so often it isn’t assessed. Some types of data also need specialized skills or knowledge to analyze and interpret, which may be beyond what is available.

Other tensions include:

- Staff capacity and resources are redirected due to grant changes, which leads to needing more capacity to retrain staff.
- It takes funding to have trained, available staff for data collection and management on a consistent basis. There’s a need to increase the consistency of funding.
- Analysis is the glamorous part of this work, and it is hard to spend the time when there’s limited capacity to prioritize good data management. But data management is an ounce of prevention to prevent the need for a pound of cure.
- There’s a need for a skilled AIS data workforce, yet there is a limited talent pool to pull from. Some challenges are that data scientists can command a higher salary elsewhere. There may also be challenges around recruitment at the data collection stage.
- Data experts have finite capacity and skills, and yet they are in demand on a variety of projects. There’s hesitancy to bring them into a new project when their availability may be limited.

◇Core best practices for supporting capacity

Increase the number of people in AIS

Get people excited about water management and data early, particularly by building data management capacity into the pipeline of skills development.

Early interest can begin in elementary school by getting kids excited about science — which leads to being interested in data. Data management skills should be built into the pipeline to science from there through graduate study.

Sell the calling and impact aspect of AIS data jobs, since these roles can rarely compete on salary with the private sector.

Roles in AIS can have a big impact, but the salaries are not competitive for data scientist or management jobs in the private sector.

Increase the capacity of people who are doing AIS work by making it more streamlined for them

Documenting best practices in a way that is accessible can help give people the tools to do better data management and increase their own capacity.

Having best practices readily available to share and access through guides and documents can help people use the tools they have more effectively, increasing capacity.

Tools that compile data or enable data sharing have a carrot built in that incentivizes the users to use them — such as presenting clean data or making access to visuals easier.

Incentives for dedicating capacity to good data practices should come at every level of a system, from supervisors down. Yet, one of the easiest ways to encourage good data practices is make the output more valuable in the moment, such as providing a clean set of data or creating usable visuals.

Building tools that allow people to keep their data and workflow as-is can be easier to get buy-in, rather than forcing them to change their approach.

By designing data tools that work within existing workflows, not everyone needs advanced data skills to contribute to broader work. This allows people to focus on the things that are most important to them, while the tool itself manages the submission and compilation of data into larger data sets.

Address gaps in the existing skillsets

Make it easy and clear for people who are managing data to learn methods that make data more usable and interoperable (such as removing trailing spaces). Widely share these tips.

Training, documentation, and other efforts to connect with people who are managing data should highlight the easy tricks that support greater data usability.

AI may be a supportive tool for addressing gaps in knowledge or technical skills that would help navigate data questions.

New tools, like AI, may help support increasing capacity to use and analyze data by serving a supplementary role. Staff can use AI to help navigate things that may seem unclear, like translating from one coding language to another. In order to effectively use AI as a tool, people need training on how to ask the right questions and use prompts that get to useful answers.

Develop systems and incentives that allow organizations to have access to people with specialized skills on an as-needed basis.

Many groups (particularly managers and people from government agencies) will not have the resources to hire their own specialized staff for things like programming, data visualization, or other topics. But having access to someone or a robust tool with those skills, either through an institution or another arrangement, can increase capacity and be an incentive for collaboration and data sharing. This would require clear data sharing standards and expectations.

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Other best practices include:

- Standardized training and methods for collection of data that roll up at a larger level (like watercraft inspections).
- Investing in hiring a data expert/data scientist who can support a whole team with skills and advice.

Data Sharing

Data sharing between people working in AIS requires communication, collaboration, and strong and aligned data management systems. While there are some existing methods to support data sharing, like good data management, data sharing requires time and incentives to do well.

Data sharing is particularly important for people focused on AIS because it's so easy for invasive species themselves to cross boundaries. This requires sharing information and knowledge across jurisdictional boundaries, such as counties and states. Not only can humans inadvertently move AIS from site to site, but they can also move through the water system to new locations.

◇Core tensions about data sharing

Expectations and requirements for data sharing vary across entities, and may result in shared data not being useful.

Things like privacy requirements, format, and metadata can vary from source to source (and for managers, sometimes these policies are set at the state level). While sometimes funders or agencies require AIS data to be made public, it isn't necessarily a helpful directive, as the data may not be shared in a format that's inherently useful to others. In addition, some of the collection and management is done by entities (such as private companies) that do not have a mandate to share the data nor make it accessible, limiting use by the broader AIS community.

"[Figuring out sharing] has felt like "extra" but the culture is changing — our funding requires that we make our data public, but not necessarily useful...even as another researcher I may not know how to use it. It might be asking too much to learn to code in R just to be able to use a data set. The data's out there, but it's not usable."

Other data sets (beyond the ones you collect) can be valuable, but it's time consuming to find the data and it's not always clear what the gaps are.

It's valuable for researchers to use outside data sources to complement their work, and often managers can use other data to inform their decision-making. But figuring out what's available takes a lot of time, and it doesn't feel guaranteed that the searching will be worth it.

"[I wish we had an] inventory of publicly available data so we knew what existed. There's no way we'd be able to standardize data collection across many states and counties, but if there was a list where we could see what data was there, that would help with filling gaps."

◇Core best practices for data sharing

Best practices raised by the group about data sharing were closely related to Collaboration & Communication and to Data Management. Please see those sections on page 13 and 21, respectively.

A Foundation of Data Management

Data Management

Data management is the organization, long-term storage, and maintenance of access to AIS data. Having the fundamentals of data management in place allows researchers and managers to analyze and make decisions based on their own data, but also supports the sharing and collaboration across different groups and individuals.

Good data management practices often feel like they require extra time and effort upfront, without the individual necessarily benefiting directly from those efforts. It can be challenging to develop and maintain good practices without standards to work from, further complicated by current conflicting standards across the field.

◇Core tensions about data management

Data management is often an afterthought, but planning for effective data use really starts with collection; management decisions made in this phase set the stage for how useful the data will be later (in an individual's work and beyond).

Both researchers and managers are most focused on their short-term goals, yet planning ahead for the end (data use) can be critical in developing a strong data management process from the beginning (while planning for collection).

“Data management and storage is an afterthought - not something we're planning for in the start. We're thinking of analysis and publication - not thinking about the long term sense. More beholden to the short term goals.”

Using different platforms can limit collaboration, but may be inherent in the structures of different organizations.

Whether mandated by an organizational requirement or because of comfort with specific programs, different people end up using different tools for their data management — from Microsoft Office products to Google Suite and other software. Some organizations prohibit access to tools like Google Sheets or Sites, leaving staff to develop workarounds to access shared data and resources. It takes time to research and choose appropriate software, and there must be institutional support to use the chosen system.

Data is organized in very different ways across different data sets, and the inconsistencies can take a lot of time to navigate.

Ideally, AIS data would be interoperable, with aligned organization and labeling. However, different organizations and institutions use different standards and nomenclature, which can take a lot of time to navigate and bring together. For example, Minnesota uses an 8-digit lake ID system, but Wisconsin and the national model are different.

“Not that anyone is doing [data organization] “wrong”, they’re organizing for their purpose and from their skill set and background, but if you try to merge [the data sets] it can be a nightmare, even with skills in data management. Like with the Lake ID system, the nomenclature is not consistent and [we’re] spending an immense amount of time trying to harmonize data sets.”

Long-term, data needs to be maintained and managed, and institutions are well-suited for this task.

Whether supporting research, public awareness, or decision-making, long-term access to AIS data is important, yet grants often focus on the short-term data management plan. Stable repositories of data are best supported by institutions or entities that have the skills and capacity to manage the data over time, such as a library system. University repositories often have a lower cost than options like Dryad. There’s also a need to ensure that data is stored in a way that supports data integrity — such as through databases as opposed to spreadsheets, and with appropriate use of master files. Long-term, there needs to be thoughtful assessment of what data is stored for retention, and what should be deaccessioned over time.

“There was a big data set stored in Word Perfect which doesn’t exist anymore, but the library had computers that could convert it and it now moves forward in time. [The librarians who maintain the data sets] have strict standards for renaming and metadata.”

Developing data standards and a data management plan takes expertise, strategy, and time that may be limited for AIS researchers and managers.

Organizations and groups may have a large repository of data, but not necessarily a data management plan and a set of standards that makes the data consistent, accessible, and stable. While some funders are now including stipulations for data management plans, the resources and guidance for these plans may not be particularly robust. It takes time, resources, and skills to develop a system that both works for the existing data and can enable collaboration with other potential data users. There currently aren’t accessible standards across the AIS community that groups could adopt and use for their management systems. Additionally, as standards are developed, the legacy of past data decisions and formats has to be incorporated into the process. For example, if most data is saved in Excel spreadsheets, but new data management standards ask for a different format, there has to be a coordinated effort and process to ensure that people do not just stay in Excel because it’s what they already have.

“We’re trying to create an internal database of projects we have run and the geographic scope of that. That’s a huge internal undertaking. Our group has been around for 30 years and...we have a massive amount of data and a lot of non-digitized stuff. We have no standards, so we’re creating our own standards — even things like how we write a file name. There’s not a centralized way. If we want to share [data] with someone do we need to take out the spaces and put underscores? When it comes to sharing, we don’t have the info on what we should be doing.”

Incentives from funders can start the process of data management, but long-term there needs to be a culture of creating and using rigorous standards.

Incentives from funders are helpful to begin to develop and use data management standards, but the motivation to continue must also come from organizational and field-wide culture in order to be sustained long-term.

“This requires institutional commitments to make this happen. The individual incentive model probably doesn’t work, because it relies too much on one person. [Data management] needs to become part of institutional culture...this comes from the top *and* from funders *and* the happy hour at the conference. It’s not coming from an extra \$5K in a grant.”

Other tensions include:

- Even when there's a lot of agreement within datasets, it's the 5% that is off that takes up a lot of time.

◇**Core best practices for data management**

Default to the highest-level data management structure available (such as the federal standards).

Not every organization is able to default to this option for their data storage, as different places may have specific expectations or requirements. But when it’s possible, it can support greater interoperability between data later, easing sharing and collaboration.

Develop a data management plan for each data asset, including dictionaries, glossaries, and good metadata.

A data management plan for each asset should use a consistent set of standards and be implementable across the team that will be interacting with it, given their capacity constraints.

Develop internal systems to reinforce consistent use of a data management plan throughout an organization.

Once a data management plan is in place, it’s also critical to develop internal systems to be sure that the plan can be put to use. Top-down reinforcement can be helpful to reinforce this use, but it also requires a culture that supports following the plan.

Document and share standards for formatting as well as workarounds people have created to manage data sets.

Creating documentation for internal use can help support a variety of team members to be aware of, and ideally follow, the standards for data management, including things like file naming structure. But an even greater benefit can be to share the workarounds that researchers and managers have created to manage data sets, and particularly to get different data sets to talk to each other. Publishing these workarounds can make them available to everyone else, and save a lot of time recreating methods.

Consider the use of university repositories or other institutional hubs to store, manage, and share data.

Not only can these hubs provide a stable, well-managed location for data, they may cost less than other options and have a mission to make information accessible already.

Other best practices include:

- Reinforce the need for good data practices and management regularly, as it can fall away from people's attention.
- Top-down approaches, including leadership by supervisors, can help increase buy-in to best practices in data management.

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